

FINLAND

INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON MANAGEMENT, ECONOMICS & SOCIAL SCIENCE

**FINNISH International Scientific Online
Conference:**

**«INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON
MANAGEMENT, ECONOMICS & SOCIAL
SCIENCE»**

A collection of articles by Asian scholars

Issue 9, Part 2

Indexed databases:

aidlix.com

INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON MANAGEMENT, ECONOMICS & SOCIAL SCIENCE: a collection scientific works of the International scientific conference – Tampere, Finland «AID», 2025. Issue 3 Part 2.

Languages of publication: English, Russian, German, Italian, Spanish

The collection consists of scientific research of scientists, graduate students and students who took part in the International Scientific online conference «**INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON MANAGEMENT, ECONOMICS & SOCIAL SCIENCE**». Which took place in Tampere, 2025.

Conference proceedings are recommended for scientists and teachers in higher education establishments. They can be used in education, including the process of post - graduate teaching, preparation for obtain bachelors' and masters' degrees. The review of all articles was accomplished by experts, materials are according to authors copyright. The authors are responsible for content, researches results and errors.

© «AID», 2025

© Authors, 2025

SECTION 1. ARTICLES FROM ASIA

1.	DATASET MA'LUMOTLAR TO'PLAMI BILAN ISHLASH. Xabibullayev Javohirbek Odilbek o`g`li	4
2.	FORMING PSYCHOLOGICAL STABILITY IN AMATEUR ATHLETES THROUGH SPORTS GAMES Raximov G`ulomjon Davronbekovich	10
3.	WPFDA STILLAR, TRIGGERLAR VA TEMALAR. Yusupov Mirsaid Abdulazizovich , Jurabayev Javohir	14
4.	LINQ SO'ROVLAR YARATISH Yusupov Mirsaid Abdulazizovich , Nurmatova Xushnozabonu To'ychiboy qizi	20
5.	WAYS TO ENSURE THE STABILITY OF NATIONAL PAYMENT SYSTEMS Hamroyeva Maftuna Axtamovna	27
6.	DIGITAL EVIDENCE IN CIVIL PROCEEDINGS Khudoynazarov Dadahon Avaz ugli	31

**FORMING PSYCHOLOGICAL STABILITY IN AMATEUR ATHLETES
THROUGH SPORTS GAMES****Raximov G'ulomjon Davronbekovich**

Independent researcher at Bukhara State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15515808>

Abstract: This thesis analyzes the importance of sports games in the formation of psychological stability of amateur athletes. Psychological stability is directly related to the athlete's ability to manage his emotional state during and outside the competition, stress tolerance, self-confidence and high motivation. The study scientifically sheds light on how sports games - in particular, team games such as football, volleyball, basketball - affect socialization, the formation of positive emotional states and volitional qualities in amateur athletes.

Keywords: sports games, psychological stability, stress tolerance, motivation, socialization, sports psychology, team games.

Introduction.

In the conditions of modern sports psychology, the achievement of high results by an athlete directly depends not only on the level of physical, but also on the level of psychological preparation. Especially for amateur athletes, the formation of psychological stability in the initial stages of their entry into sports activities is an important factor in balancing their attitude to sports, the process of self-awareness, the motivational system and the emotional state.

Psychological stability is a person's emotional and volitional tolerance to various external and internal stress factors, the ability to maintain balance and make the right decisions. In sports, this is especially important, because during each game or competition, athletes are under uncertainty, competition, team harmony and personal pressure.

Sports games are a form of activity that, along with physical activity, allows for psychological socialization, communication skills, stress management, regulation of interpersonal relationships, and the development of volitional qualities. In particular, team games such as football, volleyball, and basketball are considered an important tool in the formation of cooperation, leadership, self-control, acceptance of failure and drawing the right conclusions in amateur athletes. The thesis analyzes the psychological and pedagogical foundations of developing psychological stability in amateur athletes through sports games, effective methodological approaches, factors for optimizing the motivational and emotional state, and the psychoprophylactic value of sports training. The relevance of the study is that today, raising young people interested in sports to be not only physically but also mentally stable and resilient is considered an important social task.

Methodology:

This study was aimed at identifying effective psychological and pedagogical

approaches to forming the psychological stability of amateur athletes through sports games. Based on a comprehensive approach, the study used psychodiagnostics, experimental and pedagogical observation, testing, as well as qualitative and quantitative analysis methods. The concept of psychological stability is based mainly on components such as emotional stability, stress resistance, willpower stability, and adaptive capacity. In this regard, the study participants were selected from among amateur athletes aged 18 to 25 years. Their attitude to sports activities, psychological state, and participation in team games were studied on a systematic basis.

In the first stage, the "Psychological Stability Index" (PBI), "Emotional Intelligence Test" (EIT, based on D. Mayer and P. Salovey), and "Stress Tolerance Assessment Test" (Holmes-Rahe scale) were used to determine the initial psychological stability of the athletes. These tests assessed the participants' emotional self-control, reactive responses to external pressure, and internal psychological resources. In the second stage, the experimental group was organized to train in team sports games 3 times a week for 3 months (football, volleyball, basketball). The training was developed based on a psychopedagogical approach, in which skill-building technologies, interactive game methods, and psychocorrective exercises were integrated. In the process, the goal of each training session was not only physical activity, but also interpersonal relationships, decision-making under stress, and the arousal of positive emotions.

During the experiment, athletes' interaction, their role in collective decision-making, psychological reactions in conflict situations, and motivational dynamics were recorded through structured interviews, observation protocols, and semi-structured interviews. The data were processed based on content analysis and statistical correlation analysis, and the positive effect of engaging in sports on psychological stability was substantiated by empirical evidence. This methodological approach made it possible to study not only the physical health-improving, but also the psychoprophylactic, motivational-cognitive, and affective-volitional functions of sports. The results of the study showed that regular sports games serve as an important factor in restoring emotional balance, managing external stressors, strengthening a positive outlook, and increasing the level of socio-psychological adaptation in amateur athletes.

Results:

Based on psychodiagnostic tests, observations, experimental training, and qualitative interviews conducted during the study, a number of important results were achieved in terms of the formation of psychological stability in amateur athletes through sports games.

Firstly, it was found that the level of emotional stability significantly increased in participants who systematically engaged in sports games. This was confirmed, in particular, by the test results. According to the results of the Emotional Intelligence Test (EIT) based on the methodology of D. Mayer and P. Salovey, the indicators of

understanding, managing emotions, and emotional empathy in athletes in the experimental group were on average 17-20% higher than in the control group. This indicates that sports games serve as an effective tool for developing emotional intelligence.

Secondly, a significant increase in the level of stress resistance was observed. The results of the assessment based on the Holmes-Rahe scale showed that athletes in the experimental group reduced their level of reactivity to socio-psychological pressures, which allowed them to mobilize their internal psychological resources. Athletes who gained experience through sports games demonstrated a constructive approach to problem situations, a willingness to compromise, and an increase in social competencies in conflict resolution.

Thirdly, it was found that volitional qualities - for example, determination, self-control, concentration, and goal-orientedness - were significantly activated through team sports games. During experimental observations, the athletes' participation in collective decision-making, the choice of flexible strategies depending on the situation, and their actions in a positive spirit showed that their volitional readiness was strengthened. This is explained by the activation of internal control mechanisms, which in psychology are called volitional regulation.

Fourthly, sports games served as a powerful factor in the development of socio-psychological adaptation and interpersonal relationships in amateur athletes. Competencies such as the distribution of roles within the team, communication culture, cooperation, and mutual assistance were strengthened as a result of experimental training. In particular, athletes experienced an increase in the feeling of psychosocial support, a sense of belonging to the team, and a higher level of personal activity.

In conclusion, it was found that regular participation in sports games allows for the balanced development of all components of psychological stability in amateur athletes - emotional, volitional, motivational and communicative aspects. This confirms the importance of sports games not only as physical, but also as a psychocorrective, psychopreventive and psychoeducational tool.

Conclusion

The results of this study showed that sports games are an effective tool for forming and strengthening psychological stability in amateur athletes. The main components of psychological stability - emotional stability, stress resistance, volitional control and social adaptation - are significantly developed through sports games. The growth of emotional intelligence among the participants of the experiment, that is, the development of the ability to understand and manage emotions, allows them to adapt in stressful situations and effectively mobilize psychological resources. This, in turn, leads to athletes demonstrating a high level of psychological resilience.

Also, team sports games strengthen social psychological functions and serve to

develop communication, cooperation and leadership skills among athletes. These processes lead to the social identification of athletes, their perception of themselves as active members of the team and the formation of a system of mutual social support. As a result, they show a high level of resistance to psychosocial stress factors in their relationships. The psychopedagogical methods used in the study, including interactive game technologies and psychocorrectional exercises, were proven to be effective in harmonizing the motivational and volitional components of athletes. These methods served to develop athletes' self-management, goal-setting and constructive coping skills. In general, the formation of psychological stability through sports games not only increases the effectiveness of sports activities, but also strengthens the general psychological well-being of amateur athletes and their success in social activities. This indicates the possibilities of wider introduction of sports games as a means of psychoprophylaxis and psychotherapy in the development of psychological stability. Thus, the results of this study serve as a basis for the development and implementation of innovative methodological approaches to the development of psychological stability in amateur athletes and enrich theoretical and practical knowledge in the field of sports psychology.

References:

1. Antonovsky, A.V. (1987). The concept of stress and health. Moscow: Medicina.
2. Ginzburg, E.P., & Mukhamedzhanov, M.N. (2003). Fundamentals of sports psychology. Moscow: Fizkultura i sport.
3. Mayer, J.D., Salovey, P., & Caruso, D.R. (2000). Emotional intelligence as a standard intelligence. *Emotion*, 10(2), 140–152.
4. Vealey, R.S. (1988). Future directions in psychological skills training. *The Sport Psychologist*, 2(4), 318–336.
5. Weinberg, R. S., & Gould, D. (2015). *Foundations of Sport and Exercise Psychology* (6th ed.). Champaign, IL: Human Kinetics.
6. Zinsser, N., Bunker, L., & Williams, J.M. (2001). Cognitive techniques for building confidence and enhancing performance. In J.M. Williams (Ed.), *Applied Sport Psychology: Personal Growth to Peak Performance* (4th ed., pp. 278–304). Mountain View, CA: Mayfield Publishing.